

The CeOS Stakeholders Consultation at the European Level

ABSTRACT

The CeOS Stakeholders Consultation was held on July 2, 2024, in Limassol, Cyprus, gathering 12 key stakeholders to discuss Open Science (OS) and Citizen Science (CS) in Southeastern Europe. Organised by LIBER, the event addressed policy challenges, the role of libraries as knowledge hubs, cross-regional collaboration, and the integration of CS with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Key recommendations included strengthening policies, enhancing library support, fostering collaboration, and aligning CS with EOSC standards.

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The Citizen-Enhanced Open Science (CeOS_SE) Stakeholders Consultation at the European Level took place on 2 July 2024 (<https://ceosse-project.eu/ceos-stakeholders-consultation-at-the-european-level/>), a day before the LIBER 2024 Annual Conference in Limassol, Cyprus (<https://libereurope.eu/event/liber-2024-annual-conference/>). It brings together key stakeholders, 12 in total, from across Europe to discuss the role of Open Science (OS) and Citizen Science (CS) in Southeastern Europe. The consultation, organised by LIBER, focused on identifying barriers, sharing best practices, and exploring policy changes needed to enhance OS and CS adoption in the region.

The event was held under the Chatham House Rule, allowing participants to share insights freely while maintaining confidentiality regarding individual contributions.

This report summarises the discussions, key takeaways, and next steps for stakeholders involved in advancing Open and Citizen Science in Southeastern Europe.

The exchanges between the different stakeholders bring to the discussion the following points: libraries as knowledge hubs, challenges and opportunities within European libraries for Citizen Science, regional collaborations, and the EOOSC and Citizen Science.

The Role of Libraries as Knowledge Hubs

Libraries play a central role in the Open Science ecosystem by providing:

- Access to resources – digital, physical, and technical infrastructure.
- Support for research and learning – offering expertise, training, and guidance.
- Collaboration and innovation spaces – fostering partnerships between researchers, citizens, and institutions.

Attendees' remark/question:

- *The Citizen Science concept is a tool to offer another perspective to the citizens on libraries' collections*
- *How can libraries better support Citizen Science initiatives and enhance public engagement in scientific research?*

Policy Challenges and Opportunities

Southeastern Europe faces several policy-related challenges:

- Limited national OS/CS policies – most countries lack formal frameworks.
- Barriers to data sharing and Open Access – many CS outputs remain inaccessible.
- Insufficient funding and incentives – limited governmental support for OS/CS projects.

The discussion highlighted the importance of adopting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and integrating OS/CS into national research strategies.

Attendees' remarks/questions:

- *What specific policy changes are required to enhance OS/CS infrastructure?*
- *There are not always policies in place, and when there are, libraries are not necessarily involved or associated.*
- *Many ongoing and already existing projects contain CS elements but are not called CS projects.*
- *How can governments incentivise greater public participation in Citizen Science?*

Cross-Regional Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange

Collaboration between different European regions is essential for knowledge-sharing and innovation. Key strategies discussed included:

- Building partnerships to exchange best practices.
- Capacity-building programmes to train library staff and researchers.
- Fostering inclusivity to ensure diverse participation in CS initiatives.

Attendees' remark/question:

- *How can different EU regions collaborate effectively to enhance Citizen Science and Open Science integration?*
- *Libraries as a central access point for information and resources: libraries know what they must do and they do it, they could be more open and adapted to their end-users though, especially digitally born users and be early owner to the latest technologies.*

Connecting Citizen Science with EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) represents an opportunity to better integrate CS outputs with the broader OS landscape. Participants discussed:

- How libraries can leverage EOSC infrastructure to enhance CS support.
- Ways in which EOSC can improve access to Citizen Science data.
- The importance of aligning CS initiatives with EOSC standards.

Attendees' question:

- *How can collaboration between libraries, CS communities, and EOSC advance Open Science?*

Recommendations

Strengthening Policy Frameworks

- Advocate for national OS/CS policies in Southeastern Europe.
- Promote FAIR data principles to enhance accessibility and impact.

Enhancing Library Support for Citizen Science

- Develop training programmes for library professionals on CS facilitation.
- Encourage cross-institutional collaboration to share resources and expertise.

Facilitating Regional Collaboration

- Establish formal networks for knowledge exchange.
- Organise joint events and workshops to build stronger partnerships.

Integrating CS with EOSC

- Support CS projects in aligning with EOSC data-sharing policies.
- Encourage funding initiatives that promote CS integration with EOSC.